

TECH 25 / TOP MARKETS

1 *San Jose, CA
(Silicon Valley)*

2 *San Francisco /
San Mateo, CA*

3 *Washington, DC Region*

4 *Boston / Cambridge, MA*

5 *Raleigh / Durham /
Chapel Hill, NC*

6 Seattle, WA

7 Austin, TX

8 Denver / Boulder, CO

9 San Diego, CA

10 Madison, WI

11 Minneapolis / St. Paul, MN

12 Baltimore, MD

13 Oakland / East Bay, CA

14 Portland, OR

15 New York City, NY

16 Chicago, IL

17 Atlanta, GA

18 Los Angeles, CA

19 Columbus, OH

20 Orange County, CA

21 Dallas / Ft. Worth, TX

22 Kansas City, MO

23 Indianapolis, IN

24 Salt Lake City, UT

25 Nashville, TN

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